

Modulated Satellite Sensors

Modulated Satellite Sensor is a type of sensor that have all the three properties of a satellite sensor i.e. hyper spectral, Radar and Lidar properties in a single wavelength of the sensor. Useful for almost every purpose in any atmospheric condition. The project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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